

From Leadership to Performance: A Serial Mediation Model of Performance Management System Effectiveness and Public Service Motivation in the Public Sector

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Abstract. The drive for reform has focused on performance management and the professionalization of public sector management. While public organizations strive to achieve efficiency, effective internal processes, and performance gains, public managers and employees still need convincing of the benefits of adopting performance management systems. This study examines how performance management system effectiveness (PMSE) influences individual motivation and employee outcomes. First, recognizing leadership as a critical variable, the study investigates the relationship between leadership styles and PMSE. Second, guided by the path-goal theory and the process theory of public service motivation (PSM), the study tests a serial mediation model in which PMSE and PSM sequentially mediate the effects of leadership styles on employee outcomes, including mastery orientation, performance orientation, and job performance. A sample of local government employees in the Philippines was used to test the hypothesized model. Findings indicate that participatory and instrumental leadership styles significantly predict PMSE, enhancing PSM. The serial mediation analysis results confirm that leadership's influence on employee outcomes is transmitted through the combined pathway of PMSE and PSM.

Keywords: performance management system effectiveness, leadership styles, public service motivation, job performance, goal orientation

Introduction

The performance management doctrine has taken root in various countries due to growing criticism of the traditional rule-bound bureaucracy and input- and efficiency-based approaches' inability to manage and measure organizational performance (Isaac-Mwita, 2000). Over the past two decades, performance management systems have permeated many countries' central and local governments (Walker et al., 2010). The New Public Management (NPM) reform values have encouraged the adoption of successful performance management strategies from the private sector that are implemented in public sector organizations. Performance management has been

viewed positively as leading to better outcomes and enhancing the value and results produced by the government (Walker et al., 2010).

While performance management systems are recognized for their potential to improve organizational outcomes, research on how effective performance management systems impact individual-level outcomes, such as employee motivation and job performance, remains limited. Scholars have identified several determinants that influence the effectiveness of performance management systems. These include environmental factors (e.g., political and economic contexts), organizational capacity (e.g., human and financial resources), administrative culture, leadership style, and managerial competencies (Bouckaert & Halligan, 2008; Van Dooren et al., 2015; Moynihan, 2008). Among these, the role of leadership has emerged as increasingly critical yet remains under-theorized in public administration literature.

Building on these identified determinants, scholarly debates have emerged around what primarily drives performance management success in the public sector. The literature presents two dominant schools of thought regarding the drivers of performance management. The first emphasizes system-level reforms and institutional structures—NPM and Results-Based Management (RBM)—focusing on rules, incentives, and data-driven accountability mechanisms. The second centers on managerial behavior and cognitive framing, arguing that effective performance management depends on organizational systems, leadership, and individual motivation (Moynihan & Pandey, 2010; Van Wart, 2013).

This study contributes to the second school of thought by proposing a theory-driven and empirically-tested model that explains how specific leadership styles influence the effectiveness of performance management system effectiveness (PMSE) and, through this, shape public service motivation (PSM) and employee outcomes. By integrating path-goal theory and Perry's (2000) process theory of PSM, the study provides a sequential explanation of how leadership activates system effectiveness and prosocial motivation, filling a recognized gap in the literature concerning the mechanisms linking leadership and performance in public organizations (Fryer et al., 2009; Van Dooren, 2011). This study bridges two major schools of thought and extends them by modeling the dual roles of PMSE and PSM, thereby offering a nuanced, multilevel explanation of public sector performance dynamics. This study addresses a theoretical gap and provides actionable insights for improving public sector performance through leadership development and performance system design.

Some scholars are more concerned with leadership, which affects PMSE (Franco & Bourne, 2003). Public managers must provide comprehensive and relevant performance indicators aligned with organizational goals (Norman, 2007) while possessing adequate hands-on operational approaches and leadership skills to motivate employees to perform better (Behn, 2005). Leaders in the public sector need to oversee and guide the implementation of performance management systems; this should be a person who can direct and inspire others to achieve organizational goals. Despite the extensive body of research on public leadership offering a wide-ranging conception and perspectives (Rainey, 2014; Yukl, 2008), the role of leadership in performance management remains underexplored (Fryer et al., 2009). Limited evidence exists to clarify the relationship between leadership and performance management, suggesting that specific leadership characteristics must underscore this relationship (Van Dooren, 2011; Van Wart, 2013). Thus, while scholars

acknowledge the importance of leadership, the roles that leadership styles play in the effectiveness of performance management systems still require further investigation. Primarily, this research examines the influence of prevailing leadership styles (e.g., instrumental, supportive, and participative leadership) on the effectiveness of performance management in the local government sector.

Van Wart (2005) classified leadership actions based on the level of analysis from (1) tasks, (2) behaviors, traits, and skills, (3) style, to (4) meta-categories. According to Van Wart, tasks—the most focused level of analysis—usually allude to the discrete functions shared by a wide range of occupations. At the same time, behavior, traits, and skills are “observable patterns of leader activities used to link related tasks” (Van Wart, 2005, p. 22). Also, he argues that leadership style is a moderate cluster of behaviors or how a leader behaves in a given work environment. In contrast, meta-categories of leadership “is a huge cluster of behaviors used primarily to analyze the universe of leader functions” (Van Wart, 2005, p. 23).

Focusing on leadership style is critical because various behavioral characteristics can be applied to different situational needs. Leaders who adopt effective leadership styles (e.g., instrumental/directive, supportive, and participative) are more successful in achieving high-performance levels (Ogbonna & Harris, 2000; Park & Rainey, 2008). Although cultural and structural factors may influence performance, leadership styles and behaviors play an essential role in organizational and employee productivity (Wang et al., 2005). Some researchers argue that the success and effectiveness of performance management systems depend on their implementation (Biron et al., 2011). The path-goal leadership theory explains why leadership styles may influence the PMSE, aligning with organizational behavior and public management views. Leaders play a crucial role since they oversee all organizational and individual performance (Walker et al., 2013). According to House and Mitchell (1974), the path-goal theory posits that when leaders provide all relevant support for employees’ duties and responsibilities, those employees will be motivated to perform well and produce outstanding organizational results.

Furthermore, the path-goal theory posits that influential leaders enhance satisfaction by helping employees achieve their goals (Rainey, 2014). In this study, the path-goal theory recognizes the impact of leadership styles on the path-goal mechanism of performance management (Filley et al., 1976; House & Mitchell, 1974). For example, instrumental/directive leadership provides clear direction and expectations, supportive leadership demonstrates empathy, and participative leadership encourages the open sharing of views and suggestions (Rainey, 2014). The performance management process focuses on identifying, measuring, and developing individual performance aligned with strategic organizational goals (Aguinis & Pierce, 2008). Strong leadership support significantly enhances the effectiveness of performance management systems, for instance, by top leadership modeling fair appraisals and integrating this into strategic management (Lawler, 2015).

Acknowledging the role of individual motivation (i.e., intrinsic or prosocial behavior), this study examines how PMSE might affect employee outcomes: public service motivation (PSM), goal orientation, and performance. Drawing on Perry’s (2000) process theory, it analyzes how PMSE influences PSM—prosocial and altruistic behavior—and employee outcomes (goal orientation and job performance). The process theory explains the relationship between the antecedents and consequences

of PSM in the model. The logic of the process theory emphasizes the reciprocal causal relationships among the organizational environment, cognitive and personal factors, and individual behavior (Perry, 2000). In this context, PMSE may enhance PSM by strengthening relational contracts between leaders and employees, clarifying goals, fostering open communication, setting performance expectations, and providing feedback (Camilleri, 2007; Ugaddan & Park, 2017). This study posits that PSM can predict high goal orientation and performance from a process theory perspective and may mediate the relationship between PMSE and employee outcomes.

This study applies path-goal and process theories to explore the sequential relationship between leadership styles and PMSE and how PMSE influences PSM and employee outcomes like goal orientation and job performance. This lens considers leadership styles as antecedents, PMSE as a mediating factor, and PSM as a motivational mechanism that affects employee outcomes. This perspective aligns with the path-goal theory, which posits that leadership improves performance management systems by clarifying goals and enhancing motivation. The process theory of PSM views motivation as shaped by organizational and managerial conditions. Based on this framework, the study's overall research question is: How do leadership styles impact PMSE, and how do PMSE and PSM, serving as dual mediators, influence employee outcomes such as goal orientation and job performance?

This article is organized as follows. First, it describes the effectiveness of performance management systems and the challenges or barriers public sector organizations face. Second, hypotheses are proposed based on path-goal theory and process theory. Third, the methods section outlines the data and items used to test the hypotheses. Fourth, the paper presents the results of the structural equation modeling and bootstrapping analysis based on a sample of civil servants from the Philippine local government, followed by a discussion of the findings. Finally, the study discusses the theoretical and practical implications, limitations, and future research directions.

Literature Review and Hypotheses

Performance management system effectiveness

Performance management requires commitment and an unequivocal understanding of all elements of the organization, leadership, employees, and unions (Berman et al., 2012). Performance management includes a range of activities, including performance planning (clarifying job responsibilities and expectations), human resource development (HRD) interventions (e.g., coaching and feedback mechanisms that reinforce positive individual behavior toward performance goals), and performance evaluation (Spencer & Spencer, 2008). Furthermore, identifying the components of an effective performance management system focuses on core measurement indicators (Park & Ugaddan, 2014). Cawley, Keeping, and Levy (1998) suggest that effective performance appraisal, a performance management mechanism, can be predicted through perceived appraisal accuracy and fairness. Performance management accuracy refers to the goal congruence between employees and the organization, goal clarity, performance indicators, and standards; an appropriate performance evaluation tool based on employee strengths; and performance management adaptation (Sharma et al., 2016). Performance management fairness refers to the performance management system's justice or integrity (Sharma et al.,

2016). Similarly, the study argues that if employees perceive performance management approaches as being accurate and fair, this may contribute to the effectiveness of the performance management system (see also Sharma et al., 2016). In addition, the focus on performance management may influence PMSE (Dewettinck & van Dijk, 2012).

Performance management is a communication tool that enables employees to reach out to employees and provide relevant and valuable performance feedback regarding employees' contributions to the organization. Various scholars view an effective performance management system through employees' perception of the accuracy and fairness of the whole system (Luthra & Jain, 2012; DeNisi & Pritchard, 2006). Evidence links effective performance management systems, organizational performance (Bevan & Thompson, 1991), and positive employee behaviors (Taylor & Pierce, 1999). Ammons and Roenigk (2015) suggest that an effective performance management system may be manifested through the following doctrinal prescriptions: (a) goal clarity, (b) performance information use, (c) result or outcome-oriented, (d) engagement of political leaders in the performance management process, (e) devolved decision-making authority, (f) financial and human resource flexibility, and (g) incentives and sanctions.

Leadership styles

Public sector leadership has been the core topic in public administration and management research and is seen as a permanently entrenched socially constructed reality that can enhance organizational performance (Meindl et al., 1985; Van Wart, 2005). Leadership behavior is an essential factor influencing organizational and individual behavior for high public sector performance (Andrews & Boyne, 2010; Brewer & Selden, 2000; Meier & O'Toole, 2002; Rainey, 2009). Leaders in public-sector organizations manage people in their organizations, motivating them to perform more extraordinarily and setting out human resource management policies (Wilson, 1999). In particular, the interplay of political and administrative leaders in dyadic leadership set-ups is critical in successfully implementing performance management (Curristine, 2005; Van Dooren, 2011).

Leadership styles have been used in similar concepts but with different names. In the literature, leadership style is denoted as an aggregate of the leader's traits, skills, and behaviors (Van Wart, 2005), determined through leader and member interactions (Denhardt et al., 2013). Previous studies explored various leadership styles and behaviors and their influence on organizational and individual behavior. Examples include transformational and transactional leadership (Avolia & Yammarino, 2013; Park & Rainey, 2008; Vigoda-Gadot, 2007), leader-member exchange (Volmer et al., 2012), charismatic leadership (Avolio & Yammarino, 2013), ethical leadership (Hassan et al., 2014; Walumbwa et al., 2011), trustful leadership (Ugaddan & Park, 2019), and others. Additionally, Ohio State University's leadership study suggests the presence of two leadership factors: consideration and initiation of structure (see also Bass, 1990). Consideration denotes leaders' behavior toward the welfare of their employees, while the initiation of structure describes leaders' initiatives to organize the group in their organizations (Denhardt et al., 2013).

There are four standard dimensions of leadership style: (1) leader control describes leaders' tendencies to monitor and allow employee participation in

identifying problems and making decisions; (2) goals and performance expectations denote leaders who settle only for high work performance levels; (3) type of motivation used emphasizes the need for leaders to motivate employees; and (4) focus of leaders' attention indicates the extent of leaders' attention on employees and internal performance, as well as the alignment of environment and organization (Van Wart, 2005, pp. 285-6). According to the path-goal theory, leadership style is based on the needs of employees (House & Mitchell, 1974) or a combination of style and employee behavioral characteristics and expectations (Denhardt et al., 2013). Leadership style includes (1) directive/instrumental leadership, (2) supportive leadership, (3) participative leadership, and (4) achievement-oriented leadership (House, 1971; House & Dessler, 1974; House & Mitchell, 1974). The directive/instrumental leadership style is a task-oriented form of leadership (Fiedler, 1967) that provides direction, guidance, clear work rules and regulations, timeframes, and the coordination of work activities. Supportive leadership is a relationship-oriented leadership style that considers employees' needs by creating a friendly work environment (Bass, 1985; Fiedler, 1967; House & Mitchell, 1974). Participative leadership, also known as consultation (Vroom & Yetton, 1973), is a leadership style that encourages a friendly work environment that seeks to discuss issues with employees by considering their opinions. In an achievement-oriented style, a leader sets challenging goals, aims to improve task performance, emphasizes excellent and high performance, and shows confidence in employees' capabilities to perform and achieve the desired organizational goals.

Public service motivation

PSM is a well-established concept popular in organizational behavior and psychology literature. Various studies have argued that PSM positively influences organizational factors such as satisfaction (Bright, 2008), the commitment of public employees (Park & Word, 2012), job performance (Alonso & Lewis, 2001), and public sector organizational performance (Kim, 2005). The idea of PSM has revived the essence of public service ethics and public duty (Ugaddan & Park, 2019) and reflects intrinsic work motivation in the public sector (Park & Word, 2012; Perry & Hondeghem, 2008). As a concept, PSM captures the beliefs, values, and attitudes that manifest more significant concern for the interests of the organization and the public (Vandenabeele, 2009). Several studies have shown that PSM can be influenced by numerous factors such as personal attributes (e.g., education, family life status), sociohistorical factors (DeHart-Davis & Pandey, 2005), leadership (Park & Rainey, 2008), and contextual or work conditions, among others. In the study by Moynihan and Pandey (2007), they found that employees' perception that an organization resolutely implements reforms significantly and positively predicts PSM.

Leadership Styles, PMSE, and PSM

Based on the path-goal theory, leadership styles influence employees' behavior toward the effectiveness of organizational or managerial systems when there is a need to understand the direction and expectation, show sympathy, and encourage opinion and participation in decision-making within the organization. Specifically, directive/instrumental leadership can enhance the effectiveness of performance management systems when a leader strongly assumes leadership control and clarifies task ambiguity, work procedures, and work performance (Denhardt et al., 2013; Van

Wart, 2005). Clear communication from leaders during performance management may result in employees having specific roles and performance expectations (Ammons & Roenigk, 2015; Biron et al., 2011). Supportive leaders who show consideration for their employees may enhance the effectiveness of performance management when they foster a friendly and caring work environment. Individualized consideration and coaching in a supportive leader may stimulate an individual to positively and actively engage in the performance management process to make it more effective. Leaders portraying participative leadership styles encourage autonomy and the involvement of employees in work decisions and solving issues in the organization (Denhardt et al., 2013; Van Wart, 2005). Accordingly, leaders who employ a participative leadership approach may motivate engaged employees to work to understand the details of the performance management process.

Organizational factors may influence a leader's effectiveness in achieving their desired goals. Van Wart (2005) argues that contingency factors (e.g., characteristics related to organization, task, employees, leaders, and others) influence leadership style and behavior to be more effective. Thus, the following hypotheses are suggested:

H1a: Directive /instrumental leadership is positively related to PMSE.

H1b: Supportive leadership is positively related to PMSE.

H1c: Participative leadership is positively related to PMSE.

The study draws on the arguments of the path-goal theory linking leadership styles and PSM. When leaders provide support and assist employees in achieving their goals, they also motivate their employees to enhance their performance (Park & Rainey, 2008). In particular, a participative leadership style based on mutual respect, support, and accommodation might increase PSM (Denhardt et al., 2013). The individualized consideration and relationship orientation of supportive leadership can encourage PSM because it underscores public service norms (Caillier, 2015; Wright et al., 2012). Behaviorally, the directive/instrumental leadership style emphasizes control, clarifying roles, informing, and delegating tasks concerning job performance (Alison & Crego, 2012). Ensuring clarity and controlling employees to achieve high-performance goals includes explaining the goals of the organization as a whole and how employees may contribute to such goals in a larger form of motivation (Paarlberg & Perry, 2007) may enhance employees' PSM (Paarlberg & Lavigna, 2010).

H2a: Directive /instrumental leadership is positively related to PSM

H2b: Supportive leadership is positively related to PSM.

H2c: Participative leadership is positively related to PSM.

PMSE, PSM, and Employee Outcomes

This study considered certain causal relationships between performance management effectiveness and employee outcomes. Through process theory, the study predicts that performance management system effectiveness will influence employees' PSM, goal orientation, and job performance. PSM will mediate the link between PMSE and outcome variables.

Linking PMSE and job performance, effective delivery of performance management processes for providing meaningful feedback, coaching and mentoring, and developing performance levels may enhance individual performance (Cardy & Leonard, 2011). Boyne (2010) also argues that performance management positively affects organizational performance in the public sector. This study argues that job performance is a component of organizational performance. Thus, this study hypothesizes the following:

H3a: PMSE is positively related to job performance.

Communicating organizational, managerial, and individual goals leads to higher performance (Moynihan & Pandey, 2004). The path-goal theory explains the relationship between employees' goal clarity, motivation, and performance (Rodgers & Hunters, 1992). When employees perceive performance management programs as providing clear performance goals and effectively employing human resource development (HRD) interventions, individual goal orientation may be enhanced (see, for example, on high learning orientation, Godshalk & Sosik, 2003). Performance management processes may allow leaders and employees to discuss developmental goals—necessary knowledge, skills, and abilities in the performance of tasks—and strategically plan how to achieve them. Performance management takes on employees' life cycle and links organizational and individual goals through organizational processes (Sengupta et al., 2007; Smither & London, 2009) or the alignment of individual goals and organizational objectives. Performance management is likely to promote individual goal orientation as it provides a mechanism that develops a highly engaging organization by encouraging individuals and teams to participate in defining their goals (Armstrong & Baron, 2002). It ensures they are on the right track to achieving their goals (Bogardus, 2009). In addition, the performance management process may influence goal orientation through competitive reward structures and evaluative feedback. Therefore, this study anticipates that performance management will directly affect goal orientation. Thus, the study proposes the following hypotheses:

H3b: PMSE is positively related to mastery orientation.

H3c: PMSE is positively related to performance orientation.

Linking PMSE and PSM, this study refers to process theory. Several studies have found that PSM is influenced by numerous factors, such as personal characteristics (e.g., education, family status), socio-historical factors (DeHart-Davis & Pandey, 2005), leadership (Park & Rainey, 2008), and contextual or employment conditions (Moynihan & Pandey, 2007). Moynihan and Pandey (2004) found that employee perceptions that an organization resolutely implements reforms significantly and positively predicted PSM. Camilleri (2007) found that when employee perceptions of the organization regarding autonomy, entrepreneurship, and productivity through people were high, PSM was high. Therefore, the organizational context and various managerial initiatives (e.g., performance management) that affect employee behaviors may also influence employees' PSM (Mostafa et al., 2016). Recent studies argue that PSM is a malleable behavioral state in given organizational circumstances (Bellé, 2013). As an individual attitude toward serving and contributing to the general

welfare, PSM is vulnerable to organizational influences and is a strong antecedent of positive organizational behaviors, such as performance management systems. Thus, the study suggests the following hypotheses:

H4a: PMSE is positively related to PSM.

H4b: PMSE mediates the positive relationship between leadership styles and PSM.

PSM and Employee Outcomes

In previous studies, understanding the PSM-performance link and the direct relationship between PSM and employee behavior outcomes has received little attention (Leisink & Steijn, 2009). However, Perry and Wise (1990) argued that employees with high PSM are more likely to perform better. Subsequent studies also proved the positive link between PSM and performance by arguing that employees with high PSM perform better (Naff & Crum, 1999). Other studies also examined the direct and indirect relationship between PSM and performance. For example, Vandenabeele (2009) determined the direct relationship between PSM and performance and an indirect effect through job satisfaction and commitment.

Similarly, PSM is more likely to influence employees' goal orientation, a motivational variable that affects the desire to learn and demonstrates competence in the workplace. Finally, suppose we assume that local government sectors integrate performance management processes and are more likely to provide workers with a high propensity toward prosocial or public service values. In that case, employees' PSM will be enhanced. Thus, the study suggests the following hypotheses:

H5: PSM is positively related to employee outcomes [(a) job performance, (b) mastery orientation, (c) performance orientation].

H6: PSM mediates the positive relationship between PMSE employee outcomes [(a) job performance, (b) mastery orientation, and (c) performance orientation].

Serial Mediating Role of PMSE and PSM on Employee Outcomes

The serial mediation of PMSE and PSM on leadership styles and employee outcomes integrates insights from the path-goal theory (House, 1971) and process theory of PSM (Perry, 2000). First, the path-goal theory posits that different leadership styles (i.e., supportive, participative, and instrumental (directive)) influence employee behavior when they clarify the path to goal achievement, address challenges, and facilitate individual and organizational mission congruence and rewards. When leaders enhance employee role clarity, engage in emotional support, and employ participatory goal-setting, they can influence individual perceptions of efficacy, particularly performance management systems. Second, following the lens of process theory, scholars argue that leadership and organizational practices can influence PSM through value internalization, socialization, and mission and goal alignment (Perry & Wise, 1990; Vandenabeele, 2007; Kim, 2009). This means motivation is not a fixed trait like PSM; instead, it is subject to change, leadership styles, and organizational context. Last, the influences of leadership styles, PMSE, and PSM

in a serial mediation manner on employee outcomes (i.e., mastery orientation, performance orientation, and job performance) are aligned with goal-setting (path-goal theory), self-regulation (process theory), and achievement.

Thus, the study suggests the following hypotheses:

- H7: The effect of supportive leadership on (a) mastery orientation, (b) performance orientation, and (c) job performance are serially mediated by PMSE and PSM.*
- H8: The effect of participative leadership on (a) mastery orientation, (b) performance orientation, and (c) job performance are serially mediated by PMSE and PSM.*
- H9: The effect of directive/instrumental leadership on (a) mastery orientation, (b) performance orientation, and (c) job performance are serially mediated by PMSE and PSM.*

Figure 1 shows the relationships among constructs in the research model.

Figure 1
Research Model

Data and Method

Data

Data for this study were collected from April 25 to May 25, 2018, across five purposefully selected local government units (LGUs) in the province of Isabela, Philippines: Santiago City, San Isidro, Alicia, Angadanan, and Echague. These LGUs were chosen based on (1) their willingness to participate, (2) diversity in classification (including both city and municipal governments), and (3) geographic accessibility and logistical feasibility for the research team. This approach aligns with common practices in public administration research, where purposive selection is suitable for theory testing and contextualized model-building (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Bryman, 2012; Patton, 2002).

The survey was conducted using face-to-face interviews by trained field enumerators from the Institute of Public Administration and Governance at Isabela State University. Although the survey items were initially written in English—the official language for Philippine government communication—interviewers were instructed to translate questions into Tagalog or local vernaculars (e.g., Ilocano) as necessary. This bilingual and context-sensitive approach ensured inclusivity and comprehension. While internal listings of employees identified potential participants, survey participation remained voluntary and non-random. Therefore, the sampling strategy involved purposive site selection with voluntary, convenience-based respondent participation. A cover letter from the mayor or local chief executive accompanied the survey to encourage department heads to support the process. The survey instrument included validated scales to measure constructs such as leadership styles, PMSE, PSM, job performance, goal orientation (i.e., mastery, performance), and various organizational variables. Respondents were guaranteed confidentiality and anonymity, and no personal identifiers were collected to minimize self-report bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003).

A total of 299 responses were received, reflecting a response rate of approximately 70%. Female respondents accounted for 54.5% of the sample. The largest age group was 20–29 years (36.5%), and 63.2% of respondents held bachelor's degrees. Regarding tenure, 37.1% had between one month and three years of service. Employment statuses included permanent (36.5%), casual (29.8%), and job order (33.4%). Missing data were addressed using the Expectation-Maximization method (Dempster et al., 1977; Gold & Bentler, 2000). A detailed profile of respondents is presented in Table 1.

Table 1
Sample Characteristics (n = 299)

Variable	Category	n (%)
Local government unit	Alicia	47 (15.7)
	Angadanan	64 (21.4)
	Echague	61 (20.4)
	San Isidro	53 (17.7)
	Santiago City	73 (24.4)
Gender	Male	136 (45.5)
	Female	163 (54.5)
Age (years)	20-29	109 (36.5)
	30-39	96 (32.1)
	40-49	49 (16.4)
	50-59	31 (10.4)

	60 or older	2 (0.6)
Educational attainment	Highschool or less	11 (3.7)
	College (2-3 years)	90 (30.1)
	Bachelor's degree	189 (63.2)
	Master's degree	7 (2.3)
	Doctorate	2 (0.7)
Length of service (years)	1 month - 3	111 (37.1)
	3-5	96 (32.1)
	5-10	54 (18.1)
	10-15	13 (4.3)
	More than 15	25 (8.3)
Employment status	Permanent	109 (36.5)
	Casual	89 (29.8)
	Job Order	100 (33.4)
	Others	1 (0.3)

Measurement

The survey examined the opinions of local civil employees regarding the effectiveness of performance management systems, leadership styles, political support, public service motivation, goal orientation, and employee performance. Each variable in the study was measured using indices derived from multiple survey items based on previous research. Unless stated otherwise, the survey items included in the analysis were answered using Likert-type scales, where one (1) indicates *strongly disagree*, and seven (7) indicates *strongly agree*.

PMSE

Dewettinck's eight-item scale was used to measure performance management system effectiveness. Survey participants agreed with adopting performance management in the local government unit on a seven-point Likert scale. Illustrative items include "Performance management system motivates me, provides me with more insights into my contributions, and adds value." Cronbach's alpha for the scale was .978.

Leadership style

The leadership style was assessed using a scale developed by House (1971) and House and Dessler (1974). The scale comprises three dimensions based on the work of Ogbonna and Harris (2000): participative leadership (e.g., "Before making decisions, the leader(s) in our department consider(s) what subordinates have to say"), supportive leadership (e.g., "The leader(s) in our department help(s) people to make working on their tasks pleasant"), and instrumental leadership (e.g., "The leader(s) in our department explain(s) the way tasks should be carried out"). The factor analysis supported a single-factor dimension. The CFA supported a second-order

leadership style with three factors, and the indices have high internal consistency: participative leadership (four items, Cronbach's α : .952), supportive leadership (five items, Cronbach's α : .960), and instrumental leadership (four items, Cronbach's α : .911).

PSM

Public service motivation was measured using a 14-item scale derived from Perry (1996), with four dimensions: attraction to policy-making (e.g., "The compromises that are involved in public policy-making do not appeal to me"), norm-based (e.g., "It is difficult for me to be intensely interested in what is going on in my community"), compassion (e.g., "To me, patriotism includes seeing to the welfare of others"), and self-sacrifice (e.g., "I believe in putting duty before self"). The factor analysis results supported the distinctiveness of the four PSM dimensions among local civil employees in the Philippines. The scale reliability of the PSM dimensions is relatively high: attraction to policy-making (three items, Cronbach's α : .563), norm-based PSM (two, Cronbach's α : .912), self-sacrifice (four items, Cronbach's α : .891), and compassion (two items, Cronbach's α : .715).

Goal orientation

This item was used to assess employees' differences in goal orientation using the scales that measure mastery or learning orientation and performance orientation based on Van Yperen and Janssen's (2002) work. For goal orientation, illustrative items include "I perform better than my colleagues" and "I can demonstrate that I am the best-qualified person." Sample scale items for mastery orientation include "I acquire new knowledge or learn a new skill by trying hard" and "I learn something that makes me want to practice more." The factor analysis supported the two-factor dimensions of goal orientation. Both have relatively high internal consistency: mastery orientation (eight items, Cronbach's α : .951) and performance orientation (six items, Cronbach's α : .954).

Job performance

The study assessed job performance by measuring both in-role and innovative performance. The in-role performance items were derived from the work of Podsakoff and MacKenzie (1989), while innovative performance was evaluated following Janssen's (2000) framework of individual innovation in the workplace. Employees indicated the extent to which they agreed or disagreed with the job performance of their peers within the organization. Reliability was established for job performance (eight items, Cronbach's α : .759).

Control variables

Individual control variables, including demographic factors, include employee gender (zero (0) = male, one (1) = female), age (years), educational attainment (high school or less = one (1), college-level = two (2), bachelor's degree = three (3), master's degree = four (4), and doctorate = five (5)), length of service (years), and employment status (permanent = one (1), casual = two (2), job order = three (3), and others = four (4)). Employees' gender is a critical control variable, as the unequal upskilling experience and participation in the performance management system may lead to gender gaps

in job performance (Lyness & Heilman, 2006). Employee age and length of service are relevant factors that may influence how individuals perceive the effectiveness of performance management systems. An older employee with long tenure may have a different perspective on organizational systems due to their extensive experience.

Analytical Procedure

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) with principal component extraction and Varimax rotation was conducted to organize intercorrelated variables into underlying factor structures. However, the items used for measurement were tested and validated in previous studies; existing research employed factor analysis to confirm their applicability in a local government context. Following Anderson and Gerbing's (1988) two-step approach to validate the measurements and test the structural model, both first- and second-order factor models via confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) were utilized on the latent constructs, which evaluated the reliability and validity of the variables. Latent variable modeling through structural equation modeling (SEM) using the Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS) was employed to test the hypotheses. SEM is an advanced technique that assesses how well a structural process model connects antecedents to outcome variables through intervening factors that fit the observed data (Hayes, 2009). The estimation is grounded in a weighted least-squares parameter and a maximum likelihood-based method (Kline, 2005). Simple mediation and serial mediation analyses were conducted using bootstrapping analysis (Preacher & Hayes, 2004), a non-parametric resampling procedure that adjusts for non-normal distributions (Hayes, 2009). Employing the PROCESS macro (Model 4 and Model 6) of Hayes (2018), the study assesses the role of PMSE and PSM as mediators in the relationship between leadership styles and employee outcomes.

Results

Exploratory Factor Analysis

The self-reported measures for leadership style, performance management system effectiveness, public service motivation, goal orientation, and job performance underwent factor analysis using principal components extraction and Varimax rotation techniques. The (EFA) was carried out to assess the measurement model and provide evidence for the discriminant validity of the measures (Kline, 2005). A reliability analysis was also conducted to evaluate the internal consistency among the loaded items in the extracted factors. To confirm the adequacy of the data used for factor analysis, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was applied. As shown in Table 2, the analysis yielded 13 separate and distinct factors with factor loadings ranging from .521 to .920; eigenvalues greater than one (1) explained 83.51% of the variance.

Table 2
Factor Structure of Key Constructs

	Factors								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
<i>Leaders in our department,</i>									
Listen to subordinate's advice on which assignments should be made. (SL)	.870								
Look out for the personal welfare of group members. (SL)	.851								
When faced with a problem, consult with subordinates. (PL)	.842								
Explain the way tasks should be carried out. (SL)	.837								
Ask subordinates for their suggestions. (PL)	.830								
Maintain definite standards of performance. (IL)	.811								
Before taking action leader(s) in our department consults with subordinates. (PL)	.810								
Help people make working on their tasks more pleasant. (SL)	.804								
Listen to subordinate's advice on which assignments should be made. (SL)	.790								
Decide what and how things shall be done. (IL)	.778								
Schedule the work to be done. (IL)	.773								
Before making decisions, consider what subordinates have to say. (PL)	.757								
Do little things to make things pleasant. (IL)	.692								
Have a clear effect on how comfortable I feel in my job. (PMSE)	.807								
Provide me with clear insight into my career opportunities. (PMSE)	.806								
Motivate me. (PMSE)	.803								
Enhance my self-esteem. (PMSE)	.798								
Provide me with more insights into my personal contributions and added value. (PMSE)	.797								
Have a clear effect on my performance. (PMSE)	.795								

Contribute to my professional development. (PMSE)	.789	
Cause me to function better. (PMSE)	.777	
I learn something that motivates me to continue. (MO)	.809	
I acquire new knowledge or master a new skill which was difficult for me in the past. (MO)	.793	
I feel I am improving. (MO)	.788	
I learn something that makes me want to practice more. (MO)	.770	
I acquire new knowledge or learn a new skill by trying hard. (MO)	.707	
I perform to my potential. (MO)	.699	
I learn something new that is fun to do. (MO)	.687	
I get the maximum out of myself. (MO)	.666	
I am clearly the most productive employee. (PO)	.920	
I am the only one who knows about particular things or who has a particular skill. (PO)	.916	
I can clearly demonstrate that I am the best qualified person. (PO)	.905	
I accomplished something where others failed. (PO)	.903	
I am the best. (PO)	.865	
Others mess up, and I do not. (PO)	.812	
Creating new ideas for improvements. (JP)	.795	
Mobilizing support for innovative ideas. (JP)	.761	
Transforming innovative ideas into useful applications. (JP)	.751	
Generating original solutions to problems. (JP)	.682	
Making important organizational members enthusiastic for innovative ideas. (JP)	.663	
Meets all the formal performance requirements of the job. (JP)	.598	
Fulfills all responsibilities required by his/her job. (JP)	.521	
Making a difference in society means more to me than personal achievements. (PSMSS)		.808

Making a difference in society means more to me than personal achievements. (PSMSS)	.796	
I believe in putting duty before self. (PSMSS)	.741	
Serving citizens would give me a good feeling even if no one paid me for it. (PSMSS)	.546	
I don't care much for politicians. (PSMAPM)	.801	
The compromises that are involved in public policy-making don't appeal to me. (PSMAPM)	.791	
I have a negative perception on politics. (PSMAPM)	.747	
It is difficult for me to contain my feelings when I see people in distress. (PSMCOM)		.875
Most social programs are too vital to do without. (PSMCOM)		.875
Meaningful public service is very important to me. (PSMNB)		.558
I consider public service my civic duty. (PSMNB)		.544

Note. Extraction method: Principal component analysis. Rotation method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. PL-participatory leadership; SL-supportive leadership; IL-instrumental leadership; PMSE-performance management system effectiveness; PSMSS-public service motivation self-sacrifice; PSMAPM-public service motivation attraction to policy making; PSMCOM-public service motivation compassion; PSMNB-public service motivation norm-based; MO-mastery orientation; PO-performance orientation; JP-job performance

Measurement Validation

A second-order model was estimated using CFA to empirically determine whether a higher-order construct can be inferred from the three leadership styles: instrumental, supportive, and participatory. The second-order model exhibited an excellent comparative fit index (CFI) of .970 (where CFI > .95 is considered excellent), a standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) of .025 (with SRMR < .08 being considered excellent), and an acceptable root mean square error approximation (RMSEA) of .068 (since RMSEA > .06 is considered acceptable) (Hu & Bentler, 1999). The results also indicated that the standardized loading on each dimension was significantly associated with the higher factor leadership style: instrumental (.977, $p < .001$), supportive (.980, $p < .001$), and participatory (.935, $p < .001$).

Concerning PSM, two of the norm-based PSM items (i.e., "It is difficult for me to be intensely interested in what is going on in my community." and "I unselfishly contribute to my community.") were eliminated due to very low factor loadings. One of the compassion items (i.e., "to me, patriotism includes seeing to the welfare of others") was removed due to cross-loading. The second-order factor model of PSM demonstrated an excellent fit, with a CFI of .934, SRMR = .066, and RMSEA = .072.

The standardized second-order loading on the PSM dimensions was statistically significant: norm-based PSM = .565 ($p < .01$), self-sacrifice = .183 ($p < .01$), compassion = .167 ($p < .01$), and rational PSM = .152 ($p < .01$). In this analysis, PSM was treated at the higher-order or second-order level within the structural model.

Overall Measurement Model

CFA was conducted to evaluate the psychometric properties of the constructs in the measurement model. The measurement model demonstrated an acceptable CMIN/df of 2.441 (CMIN/df > .3 is considered acceptable), a satisfactory CFI of .904, an SRMR of .065, and an RMSEA of .070 (Hu & Bentler, 1999), with all significant standardized loadings at $p < .001$. The reliabilities of the scale were assessed using composite construct reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE). CR values ranged from .764 to .978, exceeding the cut-off value of .70 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988), while AVE values ranged from .547 to .925, which also surpassed the recommended threshold of .50 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Table 3 presents the validity measures for the variables.

Descriptive Statistics

The means, standard deviations, and correlation coefficients between the key constructs and the control variables are presented in Table 4. The results indicate a relatively strong relationship ($p < .001$) among the pairs of variables.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 5 displays the model's regression estimates (unstandardized and standardized coefficients), standard errors, CR, *p-value*, and fit indices. The overall fit shows an excellent CMIN/df of 2.324, an acceptable CFI of .906, an excellent SRMR of .074, and an acceptable RMSEA of .067, indicating that the model adequately fits the data. The findings reveal that participative leadership is significantly and positively related to the effectiveness of the performance management system ($B = .84, p < .01$). Conversely, no significant results are found from the effects of supportive leadership ($B = -.20, p = .44$) and instrumental leadership ($B = -.03, p = .83$), strongly supporting only Hypothesis 1c. The empirical analysis demonstrates a significant and positive relationship between leadership styles and PSM: supportive leadership ($B = .67, p < .01$), participative leadership ($B = .74, p < .05$), and instrumental leadership ($B = .37, p < .01$), affirming Hypotheses 2a, 2b, and 2c. Additionally, the analysis confirms the positive and significant effect of PMSE on job performance ($B = .31, p < .001$), validating Hypothesis 3a. The results show no significant relationship between PMSE and goal orientation factors (i.e., mastery: $B = .12, p = .08$; performance: $B = -.07, p = .60$); hence Hypotheses 3b and 3c are unsupported. Finally, the results corroborate Hypothesis 4a, the positive relationship between PMSE and PSM ($B = .39, p < .001$).

Table 4
Means, Standard Deviations, and Correlations Among Constructs

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
PMSE (1)	5.527	0.939	1												
IL (2)	5.786	1.074	.696**	1											
PL (3)	5.324	1.072	.615**	.920**	1										
SL	5.973	1.287	.658**	.979**	.919**	1									
PSM (5)	4.661	0.899	.277**	.269**	.264**	.200**	1								
MO (6)	6.134	0.825	.694**	.668**	.632**	.580**	.289**	1							
PO (7)	4.739	1.373	.164**	.179**	.205**	.149*	.366**	.243**	1						
JP (8)	4.887	0.818	.709**	.744**	.718**	.743**	.351**	.669**	.298**	1					
Gender (9)	0.455	0.499	0.072	0.055	0.039	0.045	0.039	0.079	0.062	0.096	1				
Age (10)	2.171	1.267	-0.052	-0.02	-0.032	-0.033	0.096	-0.038	0.111	-0.006	-0.038	1			
Education (11)	2.662	0.621	-0.034	-0.092	-0.075	-.123*	.134*	0.007	0.016	-0.033	-.142*	0.022	1		
LOS (12)	2.151	1.218	-0.019	0.015	0.006	-0.015	-0.013	0.017	0.043	-0.026	-.146*	.431**	.134*	1	
ES (13)	1.983	0.869	0.072	0.038	0.007	0.065	-0.13	-0.04	-0.098	0.028	0.049	-.281**	-.116*	-.432**	1

Note. ** = $p < .01$, two-tailed tests of significance; * = $p < .05$, two-tailed tests of significance. PL-participatory leadership; SL-supportive leadership; IL-instrumental leadership; PMSE-performance management system effectiveness; PSM-public service motivation; MO-mastery orientation; PO-performance orientation; JP-job performance; LOS-length of service; ES-employment status.

Table 5
Estimated Parameters for the Structural Model

Parameter	Unstandardized Coefficient	SE	CR	<i>p</i>	Standardized Coefficient
<i>Leadership style, PMSE, and PSM</i>					
SL→PMSE	-0.199	0.259	-0.769	0.442	-0.248
PL→PMSE	0.840	0.287	2.924	0.003	0.957
IL→PMSE	-0.032	0.145	-0.219	0.826	-0.034
SL→PSM	0.671	0.255	2.627	0.009	0.907
PL→PSM	0.737	0.293	2.51	0.012	0.910
IL→PSM	0.372	0.139	2.684	0.007	0.432
PMSE→PSM	0.390	0.071	5.48	***	0.424
<i>PMSE, PSM, and outcome variables</i>					
PMSE→MO	0.119	0.067	1.776	0.076	0.134
PMSE→PO	-0.074	0.139	-0.531	0.596	-0.050
PMSE→JP	0.308	0.062	4.941	***	0.349
PSM→MO	0.717	0.089	8.03	***	0.741
PSM→PO	0.464	0.163	2.857	0.004	0.291
PSM→JP	0.400	0.126	3.176	0.001	0.418
MO→JP	0.071	0.026	2.745	0.006	0.119
PO→JP	0.028	0.101	0.277	0.781	0.028
<i>Control variables</i>					
Gender (m=1, f=0)	0.072	0.085	0.844	0.399	0.038
Age	-0.019	0.037	-0.512	0.609	-0.025
Education	0.064	0.068	0.936	0.349	0.042
Length of service	-0.001	0.041	-0.013	0.990	-0.001
Job-status	0.047	0.054	0.884	0.377	0.043

Model fit. CMIN/df = 2.324; CFI = 0.906; SRMR = 0.074; RMSEA = 0.067; **p* < .05; ***p* < .01; ****p* < .001; PL-participatory leadership; SL-supportive leadership; IL-instrumental leadership; PMSE-performance management system effectiveness; PSM-public service motivation; MO-mastery orientation; PO-performance orientation; JP-job performance; m-male; f-female).

Moreover, PSM significantly predicted job performance ($B = .40, p < .001$), mastery orientation ($B = .72, p < .001$), and performance orientation ($B = .46, p < .01$), thus supporting Hypotheses 5a, 5b, and 5c. The levels of explained variance in the overall measurement model are relatively high. For example, the model accounts for 48% of the variance in PMSE and 67% in PSM (see Figure 2). The variance in PMSE is due to the direct effects of leadership styles and significant control variables (gender, education, and length of service). The variance in PSM is due to the effects of the three leadership styles and PMSE.

Mediation Testing

The mediation analysis was conducted using the Preacher-Hayes bootstrapping technique. The study examines the mediating role of PMSE in the relationship between leadership styles and PSM, and it also investigates the mediating role of PSM in the relationship between PMSE and employee outcomes. The bootstrapping results presented in Table 6 indicated that PMSE mediates the relationship between leadership styles and PSM. The results show a significant indirect effect of instrumental leadership ($b = .16$, BCa CI [.09, .26]), supportive leadership ($b = .17$, BCa CI [.11, .27]), and participative leadership ($b = .15$, BCa CI [.10, .22]) on PSM through PMSE. These effects are relatively small; for instance, the indirect effect of instrumental leadership represents approximately 15% of the maximum value ($k^2 = .145$, 95 percent BCa CI [.049, .228]). The indirect effect of supportive leadership is around 19% ($k^2 = .188$, 95% BCa CI [.135, .248]), while it is 15% ($k^2 = .148$, 95% BCa CI [.099, .215]) for participative leadership. These analyses supported Hypothesis 4b.

Furthermore, the indirect effects of PMSE on outcome variables (i.e., mastery orientation, performance orientation, and job performance) through PSM were confirmed. The indirect influence of PMSE on mastery orientation was significant ($b = .06$, BCa CI [.014, .166]) with a relatively small mediating effect, $k^2 = .097$, 95% BCa CI [.049, .228], representing 9.7% of the maximum value. Additionally, the indirect effect of PMSE on performance orientation was significant ($b = .18$, BCa CI [.098, .361]), which accounts for 11.4% ($k^2 = .114$, 95% BCa CI [.062, .231]) of the possible effect. Lastly, there was a significant indirect effect of PMSE on job performance through PSM ($b = .06$, BCa CI [.020, .132]), or $k^2 = .094$, 95% BCa CI [.036, .188], indicating a relatively small effect at 9.4%. These findings confirmed Hypothesis 6.

Figure 2
Structural Model Results

Table 6
Bootstrapping Mediation Analysis

	Path	<i>b</i>	BCa CI	<i>k</i> ²	BCa CI	Mediation
IL	→ PMSE → PSM	.157	.092, .262	.145	.049, .228	Partial
SL	→ PMSE → PSM	.166	.106, .271	.188	.135, .248	Partial
PL	→ PMSE → PSM	.147	.095, .223	.148	.099, .215	Partial
PMSE	→ PSM → MO	.063	.014, .166	.097	.023, .220	Partial
PMSE	→ PSM → PO	.177	.098, .361	.114	.062, .231	Partial
PMSE	→ PSM → JP	.059	.020, .132	.094	.036, .188	Partial

Note. PL-participatory leadership; SL-supportive leadership; IL-instrumental leadership; PMSE-performance management system effectiveness; PSM-public service motivation; MO-masteryorientation; PO-performance orientation; JP-job performance.

Serial Mediation Analysis

Using bootstrapping (5,000 samples), a serial mediation analysis was conducted to examine the indirect effects of instrumental, supportive, and participatory leadership on employee outcomes (i.e., mastery orientation, performance orientation, and job performance) through PMSE and PSM. The serial mediation results are presented in Table 7. The results revealed that both instrumental leadership and participatory leadership had significant indirect effects on mastery orientation via PMSE and PSM, $b = .008$, 95% CI [.001, .019] for instrumental leadership, and $b = .010$, 95% CI [.001, .027] for participatory leadership. However, the serial indirect effect of supportive leadership on mastery orientation was not significant, as the confidence interval included zero ($b = .005$, 95% CI [-.001, .016]).

All three leadership styles—instrumental, supportive, and participatory—exhibited significant serial mediation effects on performance orientation and job performance. Specifically, for performance orientation, the effects were as follows: instrumental leadership ($b = .051$, 95% CI [.029, .091]), supportive leadership ($b = .039$, 95% CI [.019, .069]), and participatory leadership ($b = .058$, 95% CI [.029, .097]). Likewise, for job performance, instrumental leadership ($b = .013$, 95% CI [.006, .023]), supportive leadership ($b = .009$, 95% CI [.004, .017]), and participatory leadership ($b = .016$, 95% CI [.008, .027]) showed significant indirect effects through the combined mediation of PMSE and PSM.

From these findings, Hypothesis 7 was partially supported. Supportive leadership had significant serial indirect effects on performance orientation and job performance via PMSE and PSM but not on mastery orientation. Hypotheses 8 and 9 were fully supported. Participative and instrumental leadership significantly influenced mastery orientation, performance orientation, and job performance through the sequential mediation of PMSE and PSM.

Table 7
Bootstrapping Serial Mediation Analysis

	Path	b	Boot SE	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI
IL	→ PMSE → PSM → MO	.008	.005	.001	.019
SL	→ PMSE → PSM → MO	.005	.004	-.001	.016
PL	→ PMSE → PSM → MO	.010	.007	.001	.027
IL	→ PMSE → PSM → PO	.051	.016	.029	.091
SL	→ PMSE → PSM → PO	.039	.014	.019	.069
PL	→ PMSE → PSM → PO	.058	.019	.029	.097
IL	→ PMSE → PSM → JP	.013	.004	.006	.023
SL	→ PMSE → PSM → JP	.009	.004	.004	.018
PL	→ PMSE → PSM → JP	.016	.005	.008	.027

Note. PL-participatory leadership; SL-supportive leadership; IL-instrumental leadership; PMSE-performance management system effectiveness; PSM-public service motivation; MO-masteryorientation; PO-performance orientation; JP-job performance.

Discussion and Conclusion

The findings of this study indicate that participative leadership is a significant predictor of PMSE, while the three leadership styles are positively associated with PSM. Furthermore, PMSE positively relates to PSM and job performance and partially mediates the relationship between leadership styles and PSM. The results also show that PMSE indirectly affects employee outcomes (i.e., mastery orientation, performance orientation, and job performance) through PSM. As always, the results must be interpreted within the study's limitations. The study utilized cross-sectional survey data, which may prevent us from making causal inferences.

The study emphasizes four significant findings regarding performance management systems in this discussion. First, it confirmed a strong, positive, and essential relationship between participative leadership and PMSE. Organizational factors, such as leadership and individual behavioral orientation, can influence public sector performance. Leadership behavior and roles practiced in the public sector can foster a more positive perspective on performance management systems. Participative leadership encourages group input and decision-making. Leaders who exhibit a participative leadership style promote autonomy and the involvement of employees in work decisions and problem-solving within the organization (Denhardt et al., 2013; Van Wart, 2005). Accordingly, leaders utilizing a participative leadership approach may motivate and engage employees to comprehend the intricacies of performance management processes. Political and bureaucratic leaders can enhance their participative leadership style by developing an effective communication network—facilitating efficient information exchange—within the organization. These findings support the path-goal theory, which suggests that leaders enhance performance by guiding and supporting employees toward their goals. Participative leaders involve employees in planning and decision-making, while directive leaders clarify expectations. Supportive leaders contribute by fostering morale and reducing uncertainty. Each style helps employees engage with performance management processes more effectively.

Second, based on the process theory of PSM, the results indicate that leadership styles indirectly influence PSM through PMSE. This finding suggests that leaders who exhibit participative, directive/instrumental, and supportive leadership styles impact PSM via PMSE indirectly. Although the mediating effects are relatively small, enhancing the effectiveness of the performance management system may further strengthen its role in a dynamic and complex public sector organization. With these findings, one might consider maintaining the performance management system with some modifications. Leaders or managers may be accountable for setting goals but should also actively engage with employees to fulfill individual and organizational performance commitments. For instance, the participative leadership style may foster employees' optimistic outlook on the performance management process by involving them in detailing tasks, promoting group learning, and allowing their participation in work-related decisions.

Additionally, the directive/influential leadership style guides and directs employees toward understanding performance expectations and the performance management process. Clear communication between leaders and employees is essential for the components of the performance management system. Given the strong tendency of performance-oriented employees to demonstrate task competence

and avoid negative assessments from others (Button et al., 1996), leaders with a directive style may encourage employees toward positive performance by behaviorally emphasizing task skills and maintaining control with high-performance expectations (Van Wart, 2005). The supportive leadership style may motivate and encourage employees to excel (Yammarino et al., 1993) through a well-implemented performance management system.

Third, the results indicate a significant direct relationship between PMSE and job performance. Previous studies have shown that effective performance management processes (e.g., mentoring, coaching, and individual development) can enhance job performance (Boyne, 2010; Cardy & Leonard, 2011). The engagement and interaction between leaders and employees through performance management can stimulate work motivation and a focus on high performance. More than just an organizational process, performance management should be viewed as an ongoing process of setting goals (both individual and organizational), assessing progress, coaching and mentoring, and ensuring that performance targets are achieved.

Fourth, drawing from the process theory of PSM, this study found that PMSE indirectly affects employee goal orientation (mastery and performance orientation) through PSM. The findings suggest that while PMSE is essential, it emphasizes the mediating roles of PSM in shaping employee outcomes. In other words, more than organizational-level PMSE is needed to enhance specific employee outcomes. These need to be complemented by suitable individual levels of affective, normative, and rational motives among employees and between employees and their supervisors. Additionally, the results of this study provide further insights for public managers and assist them in appreciating the significance of a well-tuned congruence between performance management culture and public-driven motivation as key factors that could make employees more inclined to exhibit positive behaviors.

Last, the findings reveal that participative and instrumental leadership significantly influence mastery orientation, performance orientation, and job performance through the sequential or serial mediation of performance management PMSE and PSM. Supportive leadership showed similar effects on performance orientation and job performance but did not significantly affect mastery orientation, indicating only partial support for Hypothesis 7. These results align with the path-goal theory (House, 1971), which emphasizes that leadership effectiveness depends on clarifying paths to goals and providing the necessary support. Instrumental leadership exemplifies the path-clarifying role, while participative leadership promotes motivation by involving employees in goal-setting and decision-making. Supportive leadership may fulfill socioemotional needs but lack the structure to drive learning-oriented goals like mastery.

The results also support the process theory of PSM (Perry & Wise, 1990; Vandenabeele, 2007), which proposes that PSM is not fixed but shaped by organizational context and leadership influence. In this study, PMSE enhanced PSM, which then improved employee outcomes, underscoring the role of organizational systems in cultivating motivation. This suggests that leadership styles are most effective when paired with performance systems that reinforce accountability, clarity, and intrinsic public service values. Public sector organizations should train leaders to adopt participative and instrumental leadership behaviors while strengthening performance management systems. Doing so will improve employee performance and

nurture PSM, contributing to a more effective, accountable, and citizen-responsive bureaucracy.

Suggestions for Future Research

The study employed cross-sectional survey data, which may limit our ability to make causal inferences. Additionally, the data were obtained through a non-random sampling method that involved purposive selection of local government units and voluntary participation from respondents. Consequently, the findings should not be regarded as representative of all local governments in the Philippines.

While this restricts the generalizability of the results, the study's contributions remain valuable for theory-building and contextual analysis of leadership and performance management systems in the Philippine public sector. Future research could benefit from a longitudinal design to track causality over time and potentially include a more diverse and randomized sample of public sector organizations to enhance the external validity of the findings. Exploring how cultural or regional differences may moderate the relationships between leadership styles, PMSE, PSM, and employee outcomes would also be beneficial.

References

- Aguinis, H., & Pierce, C. A. (2008). Enhancing the relevance of organizational behavior by embracing performance management research. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 29(1), 139-145.
- Alison, L., & Crego, J. (Eds.). (2012). *Policing critical incidents: Leadership and critical incident management*. Routledge.
- Alonso, P., & Lewis, G. B. (2001). Public Service Motivation and Job Performance: Evidence from the Federal Sector. *The American Review of Public Administration*, 31(4), 363-380. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02750740122064992>
- Ammons, D. N., & Roenigk, D. J. (2015). Performance management in local government: Is practice influenced by doctrine? *Public Performance & Management Review*, 38(3), 514-541. 10.1080/15309576.2015.1006461
- Anderson, J. C., & Gerbing, D. W. (1988). Structural equation modeling in practice: A review and recommended two-step approach. *Psychological Bulletin*, 103(3), 411-423.
- Andrews, R., & Boyne, G. A. (2010). Capacity, Leadership, and Organizational Performance: Testing the Black Box Model of Public Management. *Public Administration Review*, 70(3), 443-454.
- Armstrong, M., & Baron, A. (2002). *Strategic HRM: The key to improved business performance*. CIPD Publishing.
- Avolio, B. J., & Yammarino, F. J. (2013). *Transformational and Charismatic Leadership: The Road Ahead* (2nd Edition). Emerald Group Publishing
- Bagozzi, R. P., & Yi, Y. (1988). On the evaluation of structural equation models. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 16(1), 74-94.
- Bass, B. M. (1985). *Leadership and performance beyond expectations*. Free Press; Collier Macmillan.
- Bass, B. M. (1990). From Transactional to Transformational Leadership: Learning to Share the Vision. *Organizational Dynamics*, 18, 19-32. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0090-2616\(90\)90061-S](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0090-2616(90)90061-S)
- Behn, R. D. (2005). The core drivers of CitiStat: It is not just about the meetings and the maps. *International Public Management Journal*, 8(3), 295-319.
- Bellé, N. (2013). Leading to make a difference: A field experiment on the performance effects of transformational leadership, perceived social impact, and public service motivation. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 24(1), 109-136.
- Berman, M. G., Kross, E., Krpan, K. M., Askren, M. K., Burson, A., Deldin, P. J., Kaplan, S., Sherdell, L., Gotlib, I. H., & Jonides, J. (2012). Interacting with nature improves cognition and affect for individuals with depression. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 140(3), 300-5. 10.1016/j.jad.2012.03.012

- Bevan, S., & Thompson, M. (1991). Performance management at the Crossroads in Personnel Management. *Journal of the Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development*, pp. 36–39.
- Biron, M., Farndale, E., & Paauwe, J. (2011). Performance management effectiveness: Lessons from world-leading firms. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 22(06), 1294–1311.
- Bogardus, A. M. (2009). PHR/SPHR professional in human resources certification study guide. John Wiley and Sons.
- Bottomley, P., Mostafa, A. M. S., Gould-Williams, J. S., & León-Cázares, F. (2016). The impact of transformational leadership on organizational citizenship behaviors: The contingent role of public service motivation. *British Journal of Management*, 27(2), 390–405.
- Boyne, G. A. (2010). Strategic planning. In R. Ashworth, G.A. Boyne, & T. Entwistle (Eds.). *Public service improvement: Theories and evidence* (60–77).
- Brewer, G. A., & Selden, S. (2000). Why elephants gallop: Assessing and predicting organizational performance in federal agencies. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*. 10. 10.1093/oxford journals. jpart.a024287
- Bright, L. (2008). Does public service motivation really make a difference on the job satisfaction and turnover intentions of public employees? *The American Review of Public Administration*, 38(2), 149–166. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0275074008317248>
- Bryman, A. (2012). *Social research methods* (4th ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Button, S., Mathieu, J., & Zajac, D. (1996). Goal orientation in organizational research: A conceptual and empirical foundation. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 67, 26–48. 10.1006/obhd.1996.0063
- Caillier, J. G. (2015). Transformational leadership and whistle-blowing attitudes: Is this relationship mediated by organizational commitment and public service motivation? *The American Review of Public Administration*, 45(4), 458–475.
- Camilleri, E. (2007). Antecedents affecting public service motivation. *Personnel Review*, 36(3), 356–377.
- Cardy, R. L., & Leonard, B. (2011). *Performance management: Concepts, skills, and exercises*. New York, NY: ME Sharpe.
- Cawley, B. D., Keeping, L. M., & Levy, P. E. (1998). Participation in the performance appraisal process and employee reactions: A meta-analytic review of field investigations. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 83(4), 615–633. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.83.4.615>
- Currystine, T. (2005). Making government work: Performance and accountability: Whether setting targets or timetables, governments want to become more efficient. Becoming more accountable helps too. *OECD Observer*, 252–253.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- DeHart-Davis, L., & Pandey, S. K. (2005). Red tape and public employees: Does perceived rule dysfunction alienate managers? *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 15(1), 133–148.
- Dempster, A. P., Laird, N. M., & Rubin, D. B. (1977). Maximum likelihood from incomplete data via the EM algorithm. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B (methodological)*, pp. 1–38.
- Denhardt, R. B., Denhardt, J. V., & Aristigueta, M. P. (2013). *Managing human behavior in public and nonprofit organizations*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- DeNisi, A. S., & Pritchard, R. D. (2006). Performance appraisal, performance management and improving individual performance: A motivational framework. *Management and Organization Review*, 2(2), 253–277. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1740-8784.2006.00042.x>
- Dewettinck, K. (2008). Employee performance management systems in Belgian organizations: Purpose, contextual dependence and effectiveness. *European Journal of International Management*, 2(2), 192–207.
- Dewettinck, K., & Van Dijk, H. (2012). Linking Belgian employee performance management system characteristics with performance management system effectiveness: Exploring the mediating role of fairness. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*. 806–825. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2012.700169>
- Fiedler, F. (1967). *A theory of leadership effectiveness*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Filley, A.C., House, R.J., & Kerr, S. (1976). *Managerial process and organizational behavior*. Glenview, IL: Scott Foresman.

- Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error: Algebra and statistics. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 382-388.
- Franco, M., & Bourne, M. (2003). Factors that play a role in “managing through measures.” *Management Decision*, 41(8), 698-710.
- Fryer, K., Antony, J., & Ogden, S. (2009). Performance management in the public sector. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 22(6), 478-498.
- Godshalk, V. M., & Sosik, J. J. (2003). Aiming for career success: The role of learning goal orientation in mentoring relationships. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 63(3), 417-437.
- Gold, M. S., & Bentler, P. M. (2000). Treatments of missing data: A Monte Carlo comparison of RBHDI, iterative stochastic regression imputation, and expectation-maximization. *Structural Equation Modeling*, 7(3), 319–355. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15328007SEM0703_1
- Hassan, S., Wright, B. E., & Yukl, G. (2014). Does ethical leadership matter in government? Effects on organizational commitment, absenteeism, and willingness to report ethical problems. *Public Administration Review*, 74(3).
- Hayes, A. F. (2009). Beyond Baron and Kenny: Statistical mediation analysis in the new millennium. *Communication Monographs*, 76(4), 408–420.
- Hayes, A. F. (2018). *Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis: A regression-based approach* (2nd ed.). New York, NY: The Guilford Press
- House, R. J. (1971). A path-goal theory of leader effectiveness. *Administrative Science House*, 16(3), 321–339. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2391905>
- House, R. J., & Dessler, G. (1974). The path-goal theory of leadership: Some post hoc and a priori tests. In J. G. Hunt & L. L. Larson (Eds.), *Contingency approaches to leadership* (pp. 29-55). Carbondale, IL: Southern Illinois University Press.
- House, J., & Mitchell, T. R. (1974). The path-goal theory of leadership: Some post hoc and a priori tests. In J. G. Hunt & L. L. Larson (Eds.), *Contemporary Business* (pp. 81-98). Carbondale, IL: Southern Illinois University Press.
- Hu, L. T., & Bentler, P. M. (1999). Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 6(1), 1-55.
- Isaac Mwita, J. (2000). Performance management model: A systems-based approach to public service quality. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 13(1), 19–37.
- Janssen, O. (2000). Job demands, perceptions of effort-reward fairness and innovative work behavior. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 73(3), 287–302.
- Kim, S. (2005). Gender differences in the job satisfaction of public employees: A study of Seoul Metropolitan Government, Korea. *Sex Roles*, 52, 667–681. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-005-3734-6>
- Kline, R.B. (2005). *Principles and practice of structural equation modeling* (2nd Edition Ed.). New York: The Guilford Press.
- Lawler III, E. E. (2015, April 15). Performance management: The three important features you are forgetting. *Forbes*. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/edwardlawler/2015/04/15/performance-management-yet-another/?sh=6c16692b2d9c>
- Leisink, P., & Steijn, B. (2009). Public service motivation and job performance of public sector employees in the Netherlands. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 75(1), 35-52.
- Luthra, P., & Jain, M. (2012, May 3). India's performance management problem: All systems for evaluating and rewarding employees fail if workers question those systems' credibility. *Gallup Business Journal*. <https://news.gallup.com/businessjournal/153278/india-performance-management-problem.aspx>
- Lyness, K. S., & Heilman, M. E. (2006). When fit is fundamental: Performance evaluations and promotions of upper-level female and male managers. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 91(4), 777-785.
- Meier, K. J., & O'Toole, L. J. (2002). Public management and organizational performance: The effect of managerial quality. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, 21(4), 629–643.
- Meindl, J. R., Ehrlich, S. B., & Dukerich, J. M. (1985). The romance of leadership. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 30(1), 78–102. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2392813>

- Moynihan, D. P., & Pandey, S. K. (2004). Testing how management matters in an era of government by performance management. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 15(3), 421-439.
- Moynihan, D.P., & Pandey, S.K. (2007). Finding Workable Levers over Work Motivation: Comparing Job Satisfaction, Job Involvement, and Organizational Commitment. *Administration & Society*, 39, 803-832. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0095399707305546>
- Naff, K. C., & Crum, J. (1999). Working for America: Does public service motivation make a difference? *Review of Public Personnel Administration*, 19(4), 5-16.
- Norman, R. (2007). Managing outcomes while accounting for outputs: Redefining “public value” in New Zealand’s performance management system. *Public Performance and Management Review*, 30(4), 536-549.
- Ogbonna, E., & Harris, L. C. (2000). Leadership style, organizational culture, and performance: empirical evidence from UK companies. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 11(4), 766-788.
- Paarlberg, L. E., & Lavigna, B. (2010). Transformational leadership and public service motivation: Driving individual and organizational performance. *Public Administration Review*, 70(5), 710-718.
- Paarlberg, L. E., & Perry, J. L. (2007). Values management: Aligning employee values and organization goals. *The American Review of Public Administration*, 37(4), 387-408.
- Park, S. M., & Rainey, H. G. (2008). Leadership and public service motivation in US federal agencies. *International Public Management Journal*, 11(1), 109-142.
- Park, S. M., & Word, J. (2012). Driven to service: Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation for public and nonprofit managers. *Public Personnel Management*, 41(4), 705-734.
- Patton, M. Q. (2002). *Qualitative Research and evaluation methods* (3rd ed.).
- Perry, J. L. (1996). Measuring public service motivation: An assessment of construct reliability and validity. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 6(1), 5-22.
- Perry, J. L. (2000). Bringing society in: Toward a theory of public-service motivation. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory: J-PART*, 10(2), 471-488.
- Perry, J. L., & Hondeghem, A. (2008). Building theory and empirical evidence about public service motivation. *International Public Management Journal*, 11(1), 3-12.
- Perry, J. L., & Wise, L. R. (1990). The motivational bases of public service. *Public Administration Review*, 50, 367-373.
- Podsakoff, P. M., & MacKenzie, S. B. (1989). *A second generation measure of organizational citizenship behavior*. Unpublished manuscript, Indiana University, Bloomington
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Lee, J. Y., & Podsakoff, N. P. (2003). Common method biases in behavioral research: A critical review of the literature and recommended remedies. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(5), 879.
- Preacher, K. J., & Hayes, A. F. (2004). SPSS and SAS procedures for estimating indirect effects in simple mediation models. *Behavior Research Methods, Instruments, and Computers*, 36(4), 717-731.
- Rainey H. G. (2009). *Understanding and managing public organizations* (4th ed.). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Rainey, H. G. (2014). *Understanding and managing public organizations*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Rodgers, R., & Hunter, J. E. (1992). A foundation of good management practice in government: Management by objectives. *Public Administration Review*, 52(1), 27-39.
- Sengupta, S., Whitfield, K., & McNabb, B. (2007). Employee share ownership and performance: golden path or golden handcuffs? *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 18(8), 1507-1538.
- Sharma, N. P., Sharma, T., & Agarwal, M. N. (2016). Measuring employee perception of performance management system effectiveness: Conceptualization and scale development. *Employee Relations*, 38(2), 224-247. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ER-01-2015-0006>
- Smither, J. W., & London, M. (Eds.). (2009). *Performance management: Putting research into action* (Vol. 21). John Wiley & Sons.
- Spencer, L. M., & Spencer, P. S. M. (2008). *Competence at Work models for superior performance*. New York: USA: John Wiley & Sons.

- Taylor, P.J., & Pierce, J.L. (1999). Effects of introducing a performance management system on employees' subsequent attitudes and effort. *Public Personnel Management*, 28, 423–452.
- Ugaddan, R. G., & Park, S. M. (2014). Unraveling the effects of leadership and motivation factors on employee engagement: Evidence from the U.S. federal agencies. *Philippine Journal of Public Administration*, 58(1), 27–58.
- Ugaddan, R.G., & Park, S.M. (2017). Quality of leadership and public service motivation: A social exchange perspective on employee engagement. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 30(3), 270–285. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPSM-08-2016-0133>
- Ugaddan, R. G., & Park, S. M. (2019). Do trustful leadership, organizational justice, and motivation influence whistle-blow intention? Evidence from federal employees. *Public Personnel Management*, 48(1), 56–81.
- Van Dooren, W. (2011). Better performance management: Some single-and double-loop strategies. *Public Performance & Management Review*, 34(3), 420–433.
- Van Dooren, W., Bouckaert, G., & Halligan, J. (2015). *Performance management in the public sector*. Routledge.
- Van Wart, M. (2005). *Dynamics of leadership in public service: Theory and practice*. New York, NY: ME Sharpe.
- Van Wart, M. (2013). Lessons from leadership theory and the contemporary challenges of leaders. *Public Administration Review*, 73(4), 553–565.
- Van Yperen, N. W., & Janssen, O. (2002). Fatigued and dissatisfied or fatigued but satisfied? Goal orientations and responses to high job demands. *Academy of Management Journal*, 45(6), 1161–1171.
- Vandenabeele, W. (2009). The mediating effect of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on self-reported performance: more robust evidence of the PSM-performance relationship. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 75(1), 11–34.
- Vigoda-Gadot, E. (2007). Leadership style, organizational politics, and employees' performance: An empirical examination of two competing models. *Personnel Review*, 36(5), 661–683. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00483480710773981>
- Volmer, J., Binnewies, C., Sonnentag, S., & Niessen, C. (2012). Do social conflicts with customers at work encroach upon our private lives? A diary study. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 17(3), 304–315.
- Vroom, V. H., & Yetton, P. W. (1973). *Leadership and decision-making*. University of Pittsburgh Press
- Walker, R. M., Boyne, G. A., & Brewer, G. A. (Eds.). (2010). *Public management and performance: Research directions*. Cambridge University Press.
- Walumbwa, F., Mayer, D., Wang, P., Wang, H., & Workman, K. M., & Christensen, A. (2011). Linking ethical leadership to employee performance: The roles of leader-member exchange, self-efficacy, and organizational identification. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 115(2), 204–213.
- Wang, H., Law, K. S., Hackett, R. D., Wang, D., & Chen, Z. X. (2005). Leader-member exchange as a mediator of the relationship between transformational leadership and followers' performance and organizational citizenship behavior. *Academy of Management Journal*, 48(3), 420–432.
- Wilson, T.D. (1999). Models in information behaviour research. *Journal of Documentation*, 55(3), 249–270. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EUM0000000007145>
- Wright, B. E., Moynihan, D. P., & Pandey, S. K. (2012). Pulling the levers: Transformational leadership, public service motivation, and mission valence. *Public Administration Review*, 72(2), 206–215.
- Yammarino, F. J., Spangler, W. D., & Bass, B. M. (1993). Transformational leadership and performance: A longitudinal investigation. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 4(1), 81–102.
- Yukl, G. (2008). How leaders influence organizational effectiveness. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 19(6), 708–722.

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